

MANAGEMENT OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT (CPD) PROGRAM IN IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF INDONESIAN LANGUAGE TEACHERS AT MGMP INDONESIAN LANGUAGE 0002 and 0032 MTs LEVEL IN SUKABUMI REGENCY

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Abstract

Continuous professional development (CPD) is the development of competencies for teachers according to needs and is carried out in stages and continuously. However, in reality, the CPD is still partial, has not demonstrated sustainability, and has not been implemented optimally. In general, this research aims to obtain an overview and analyze CPD management in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs levels in Sukabumi Regency. Specifically, this research aims to obtain an overview and analyze the planning, organizing, actuating, controlling, problems faced, and solutions to CPD problems. The theory used is the management function of G.R. Terry and the CPD Concept from PMA No. 38 of 2018. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method, as well as interview, observation, case study and triangulation techniques. The results of the research are that the planning of the CPD program is in accordance with the planning concept of G.R. Terry and also supported by rational logical values, the organization of CPD is in accordance with the organizing concept of G.R. Terry and also supported by ethical-legal values, the actuating of the CPD is in accordance with the actuating concept of G.R. Terry and the philosophy of constructivism, CPD controlling is in accordance with the controlling concept of G.R. Terry and also supported by teleological values, the problems faced by CPD are the lack of teacher presence in CPD, lack of mastery of ICT by teachers, lack of complete facilities at the place where CPD is implemented, and lack of operational costs for MGMP whose members are more than 25 people, and the solution to the CPD problem is building effective communication with madrasa heads, holding additional meetings outside the schedule via zoom, choosing MTsN with more complete facilities, and reducing operational costs. The conclusion of this research is that CPD management in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the management function of G.R. Terry and the philosophy of constructivism, and also supported by Achmad Sanusi's six value systems because they have paid attention to rational logical, ethical, legal and teleological values, although they have not been supported by analysis of available data so that CPD has not achieved its stated goals.

Keywords: Continuous Professional Development, Pedagogical Competency, Indonesian Language Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the main pillars in a country's development. In Indonesia, the role of teachers is very vital in the education process. To improve the quality of education, teachers

are needed who have high competence and continue to develop. Therefore, the Continuous Professional Development Program, hereinafter referred to as CPD, is very important. CPD aims to improve teacher competency through various activities and structured development programs.

CPD for madrasa teachers under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia is regulated in Minister of Religion Regulation (PMA) Number 38 of 2018 concerning Teacher CPD. It states that Teacher CPD is competency development for teachers in accordance with needs and is carried out in stages and continuously. Teacher CPD is implemented with the principles of comprehensive, independent, measurable, affordable, multi-approach and inclusive.

In the PMA it is also stated that Teacher CPD is carried out on civil servant teachers who work in educational units organized by the Ministry, PNS Religious Education teachers who work in educational units organized by regional governments and other ministries, Ministry civil servant teachers who work in educational units that organized by the community, non-civil servant teachers who work in educational units organized by the Ministry, non-civil servant teachers who work in educational units in the Ministry's guidance organized by the community; and Non-PNS Religious Education teachers who serve in educational units organized by regional governments, other ministries, and those organized by the community.

In the Regulation of the Minister of State for Empowerment of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform Number 16 of 2009 concerning Teacher Functional Positions and Credit Scores, it is stated that the CPD component consists of self-development, scientific publications and innovative work. In relation to self-development, this includes functional education and training and other self-development activities carried out by teachers themselves, teacher work forums, or professional teacher associations/organizations, such as Subject Teachers' Conferences (MGMP) which are held through the stages of planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling.

CPD planning is carried out in stages from education units, Ministry of Religion Offices, Regional Offices, to the Secretariat General and Directorate General including participant selection, teacher controlling, analysis of professional development needs, professional development plans, and development of CPD materials and guidelines. Teacher controllings are carried out to determine the teacher's initial competency and performance and the results of this controlling are used as the basis for preparing individual teacher competency profiles and teacher professional development plans.

Regarding actuating, CPD is organized by the government, regional government, education providers, teacher work forums, professional teacher associations/organizations, or related institutions or organizations and can collaborate with other parties through face-to-face methods and/or online. Teacher CPD organizers must prepare program actuating plans, develop curricula, assess participants' progress and learning outcomes, issue training certificates and/or competency certificates, and build learning communities in their environment to improve teacher competency.

Monitoring and evaluation of CPD is carried out by the Ministry, Regional Offices and the Office of the Ministry of Religion to assess the effectiveness, efficiency and accountability of implementing CPD. As a final step, the CPD organizer reports the actuating of the CPD to the Office of the Ministry of Religion.

From the results of preliminary research, it turns out that the actuating of the CPD program in the field still faces various obstacles, namely first, the CPD program has not yet reached all existing teachers, especially non-ASN teachers. Second, the actuating of the CPD program has not been supported by adequate resources, both teachers as participants and facilitators. Third, the actuating of the CPD has not been supported by the necessary facilities and infrastructure. Fourth, the limited participant quota means that not all teachers can take part in this activity. Fifth, the material is not appropriate to the needs of teachers and students. Sixth, during the In-1 activity where the teachers had to carry out teaching practice simulations, the average learning method used was lecture even though the Learning Actuating Plan stated the Jig Saw method. In the reflection activity, after confirmation, the result was that the teachers actually did not understand the syntax or learning steps using the Jig Saw method. Seventh, in terms of actuating time, the CPD program is delayed from what was scheduled in the proposal. This was caused by the delay in disbursement of funds so that the CPD program had to be carried out in a shorter time than had been scheduled. Eighth, there has been no clear controlling of participants' progress and learning outcomes from the organizers.

Regarding the limited quota for CPD participants, Tampubolon, Karnati, & Sugiarto (2023:78-79) argue that "However, in its actuating, there are still obstacles. The first obstacle is that the quota of participants is very limited so that not all teachers can immediately participate in functional training and teacher collective activities." Wijiutami, Wahjoedi, & Djatmika (2020:667) also argue that "Teachers reveal the obstacles they face, namely that in CPD activities, teachers are given material that is sometimes not related to what students need." Pratama (2018) stated that "professional development of vocational school teachers is still partial, has not shown sustainability, and has not been implemented optimally". Therefore, it is necessary to research the problem of the CPD program to find out the root of the problem so that alternative solutions to the problem can be found.

The researcher chose the research location at the Indonesian Language MGMP MTs level because: first, MGMP is the target of the CPD program currently being organized by the Ministry of Religion. Second, the Indonesian Language MGMP MTs level is the most numerous MGMP identified in Sukabumi Regency, namely 11 MGMPs. Third, of the 11 MGMPs, there are 5 Indonesian Language MGMPs at MTs Level in Sukabumi Regency which received assistance/funding from the Madrasah Reform Project in 2023. Fourth, of the 5 MGMPs receiving assistance, Indonesian Language MGMP 0002 was chosen because it has the largest number of members, namely 29 people and MGMP 0032 because the number of members is at least 15 people.

In general, the aim of this research is to obtain an overview and analyze the management of the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs Level in Sukabumi Regency. Specifically,

this research aims to obtain an overview and analyze the planning, organizing, actuating, controlling, problems faced, and solutions to problems in the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs Level in Sukabumi Regency.

Theoretically, it is hoped that the results of this research can develop scientific knowledge related to the management of CPD programs in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs). Practically, the results of this research can be used as input for madrasah supervisors to develop CPD program management in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs), for madrasah principals to carry out CPD program management in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs), for MGMP to carry out management of the CPD Program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs), for teachers to carry out management of the CPD Program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs), and for further researchers as reference material for further research on the management of the CPD Program in improving the pedagogical competence of teachers in other subjects at other levels of education.

This research is based on philosophical schools. Since the competencies possessed by teachers are the result of building on the various knowledge they have obtained through the education they have participated in, the philosophical flow that is in line is constructivism. According to von Glaserfeld, constructivism is a philosophy of knowledge that emphasizes that our knowledge is the result of our own construction (Pannen, 2001). This research is also based on six value systems according to Sanusi (2017), namely theological, ethical-legal, aesthetic, logical-rational, physical-physiological and teleological values.

The theory used in this research is the management function theory of George R. Terry. Terry (2005) divides four basic management functions, namely planning, organizing, actuating and controlling. The CPD concept uses PMA No. 38 of 2018 concerning Teacher CPD, namely Teacher CPD is the development of competencies for teachers according to needs and is carried out in stages and continuously.

In implementing the CPD program, teachers as CPD participants carry out learning activities. Learning theory refers to Bloom as quoted by Hanafy (2014) that 'learning is a change in the quality of a person's cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities to be able to improve their standard of living both as a person and member of society or as a creature of God Almighty'.

The impact of the CPD program is an increase in teacher pedagogical abilities as an output. Pedagogical competence refers to the concept of Mulyasa (2006), "pedagogical competence is the ability that teachers must have in understanding the characteristics of students from physical, moral, social, cultural, emotional and intellectual aspects, mastering learning theories and educational learning principles, mastering the curriculum related to the subject/field of development taught, organizing educational learning, utilizing information and communication

technology for learning purposes, facilitating the development of potential, communicating effectively, empirically and politely with students, carrying out controllings and evaluations for the benefit of learning, taking reflective action to improve the quality of learning”.

Increasing teacher pedagogical competence will also have an impact on improving the quality of learning as an outcome of the CPD program. Learning quality is the ability possessed by a school to organize learning effectively and efficiently, resulting in high value benefits for achieving predetermined teaching goals.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative approach. As McMillan & Schumacher argue in Syamsuddin (2006), ‘qualitative research is an approach which is also called an investigative approach because researchers usually collect data by meeting face to face and interacting with people at the research site’. The method used is the case study method. According to Darmadi (2014: 291), "case study research is a study that explores a problem with detailed boundaries, has in-depth data collection, and includes various sources of information."

The data collection techniques used in this research are interviews, observation, documentation studies, and triangulation. As stated in the opinion of (Nadzir, 1988:24), data collection is a systematic and standard process for obtaining the required data. The instruments used were interview guidelines, observation guidelines, and documentation study guidelines.

The location of this research is MGMP Bahasa Indonesia 0002 and 0032 Level MTs in Sukabumi Regency. The research subjects were MGMP administrators, CPD program participants, Madrasah Heads, and Indonesian language course supervisors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. CPD Program Planning

According to G. R. Terry (2005), what is meant by planning is selecting facts and connecting facts as well as making and using estimates or assumptions for the future by describing and formulating the activities needed to achieve the desired results. . Planning is also the process of thinking about and organizing the activities needed to achieve the desired goals. Planning involves the creation and maintenance of specific organizational operations. This thought process is important for the refinement of goals and their integration with other plans.

The planning for the CPD program carried out in MGMP 0002 and 0032 begins with formulating the number of educators who will be included in the CPD program. Educators, in this case, Indonesian language teachers, are the raw input whose pedagogical competence will be improved. Determining the number of educators is very important because it will be related to the funds needed to carry out the activities later. The results of the research show that the number of educators included in this CPD program is a minimum of 15 people and a maximum of 30 people, which is officially stated in the Decree of the Head of the Sukabumi Regency Ministry of Religion Office regarding the determination of the management of the Indonesian

Language MGMP. Every activity certainly requires funds to implement it, so the next planning carried out by MGMP 0002 and 0032 is to formulate the amount of funds needed for CPD program activities and where these funds can be obtained from. The funds required are Rp. 30,000,000.00 (thirty million rupiah). This refers to PMK Number 60/PMK.02/2021 concerning Input Cost Standards (SBM) for Fiscal Year 2023 by paying attention to the principles of fairness, order, efficiency, economy, effectiveness, transparency and responsibility by paying attention to a sense of justice and propriety. Funding for the CPD program comes from the World Bank through the project "Realizing Education's Promise: Component 3 – Policy and Continuous professional development for teachers and education personnel of MoRA schools".

The next step is to formulate the facilities and infrastructure needed for CPD program activities. Regarding infrastructure, determining a location for implementing a CPD program is usually more influenced by the objectives, nature, actuating time and budget. The place for carrying out activities is a madrasah which has adequate facilities and is affordable for all MGMP members. If there is no such place, you can use a meeting room around the madrasa or the local district/city Ministry of Religion building. The supporting facilities for activities prepared, as stated by the MGMP chairman, are in the form of actuating places; activity administration; stationery equipment; infocus equipment, sound system; practice materials; consumption; and other necessary means.

Next is to formulate a CPD work program, namely carrying out self-development through collective teacher activities at MGMP in the form of Technical Guidance (Bimtek) with an In-On-In pattern. This is easier for teachers to reach and accommodates non-ASN teachers who have never had the opportunity to become training participants at the Religious Education and Training Center of the Ministry of Religion. The next step is to formulate the time needed for the CPD program from planning to controlling. This CPD process requires quite a long time in planning and actuating, namely 10 months.

Finally, formulate how to carry out the CPD program. MGMP 0002 and 0032 are carried out face to face and interact directly with the instructor as facilitator and other participants and some are carried out independently. In-On-In learning activities consist of In-Service Training (In)1 activities, On-the-Job Learning (On) activities and In-Service Training (In) activities which are face-to-face learning activities at the beginning of the activity which are termed In - 1, while face-to-face activities at the end of the activity are given the term In-2. Meanwhile, On-the-Job Learning (On) is a continuation of the learning process from In-1 activities. While on, participants deepen the material and implement it with students at their respective MTs.

From the results of the research above, the CPD program planning in MGMP 0002 and 0032 includes the process of selecting facts, connecting them, making estimates for the future, formulating activities needed to achieve goals, and organizing program operations. Apart from that, rational logical values color the planning of the CPD program in MGMP 0002 and 0032 with an analysis of the needs for the number of educators, funds, facilities and infrastructure, work programs, time and clear ways to achieve the goal, namely increasing the pedagogical competence of Indonesian language teachers at MTs.

B. Organizing the CPD Program

According to G.R. Terry as quoted by Sukarna (2011) states that organizing is determining, grouping and arranging the various activities needed to achieve goals, the placement of people (employees), towards these activities, the provision of physical factors suitable for the needs work and appointment of authority relations, which are delegated to each person in connection with the actuating of each expected activity. Organizing involves assigning tasks, grouping tasks into departments, delegating authority, and allocating resources across the organization. During the organizing process, managers coordinate employees, resources, policies, and procedures to facilitate the goals identified in the plan. Organizing is complex and often involves a systematic review of human resources, finances, and priorities.

Based on the research results, organizing the CPD program begins with determining the tasks that must be carried out, grouping the work, and standard operational mechanisms or procedures so that the CPD program can be implemented according to plan. Determining tasks that must be carried out and grouping work cannot be separated. This is very closely related to positions in the management at MGMP along with their duties and functions which are adjusted to the needs of the CPD program itself.

The chairman is tasked with preparing strategic plans for the integration of the CPD Program in MGMP activities, leading special meetings that focus on implementing the CPD Program, coordinating with external parties and madrasas to support the actuating of the CPD Program, ensuring that the CPD Program is in accordance with the development needs of MGMP members. The Secretary is tasked with recording and documenting activities related to the CPD Program at MGMP meetings, compiling periodic progress reports on the CPD Program, as well as managing archives and documents related to the actuating of the CPD Program. The Treasurer is tasked with managing the budget and allocation of funds to support the actuating of the CPD Program, recording income and expenditure related to the CPD Program, and preparing special financial reports related to the CPD Program.

The Program Planning and Actuating Sector is tasked with designing and compiling training programs and development activities that are integrated with the CPD Program, ensuring that the actuating of the CPD Program is in accordance with the predetermined schedule and objectives, as well as managing evaluation and feedback from MGMP members regarding the actuating of the CPD Program. The Career and Professional Development Sector is tasked with preparing and implementing career development programs in accordance with the CPD Program, encouraging the participation of MGMP members in external professional development activities related to the CPD Program, as well as identifying the career and professional development needs of MGMP members in the context of the CPD Program. The Public Relations and Cooperation Sector is tasked with establishing relationships with external parties, including educational institutions and communities that can support the CPD Program, communicating the results of the CPD Program to the community, parents of students and the media, building collaboration with MGMP from other regions in implementing the CPD Program. Members are tasked with actively participating in CPD Program activities organized

by MGMP, contributing ideas, experience and expertise for program development, as well as involving themselves in evaluation and feedback activities related to the CPD Program.

MGMP 0002 and 0032 carry out everything from proposal selection, actuating of the CPD program, mechanisms for disbursing and using CPD program funds, determining results, duties and responsibilities of the parties, as well as monitoring and reporting in accordance with Decree of the Director General of Islamic Education (Kepdirjen) No. 1324 of 2023 concerning Technical Instructions for Assistance to the Working Group of Teachers and Madrasah Education Personnel for Fiscal Year 2023. This shows that ethical-legal values color the organization of the CPD program in MGMP 0002 and 0032 by ensuring that the program operates in accordance with all applicable laws and regulations.

The research results show that the organization of the CPD program in MGMP 0002 and 0032 includes a process of structuring activities to achieve the goals of the CPD program. This includes assigning people and establishing authority relationships. In organizing, tasks are assigned, grouped into areas, authority is delegated, and resources are allocated across the organization. The chairman is responsible for coordinating parties, resources, policies and procedures to achieve planned goals. This is represented in the MGMP organizational structure which has been decreed.

C. Actuating of the CPD Program

According to George R. Terry (2005), mobilization/actuating is arousing and encouraging all group members to desire and work hard to achieve goals sincerely and in harmony with the planning and organizing efforts of the leadership. Mobilization/actuating is the use of influence to motivate group members to achieve organizational goals. Managers must be able to make employees want to participate in achieving organizational goals.

Actuating of the CPD program in Indonesian MGMP 0002 and 0032 in Sukabumi Regency includes first, an action plan. MGMP's action plan before implementing the CPD program includes budget planning by allocating sufficient budget to implement the CPD program and compiling detailed costs for training activities or material development, scheduling activities by determining the schedule for implementing the CPD program, including the time and duration of each activity and compiling an activity calendar. which takes into account the teaching and learning schedule and other madrasah activities, procurement of materials and resources by identifying and preparing the required learning materials or modules and collecting resources such as reference books, software or necessary equipment. Apart from that, selecting resource persons or facilitators who have expertise and experience in accordance with the CPD program theme and coordinating with resource persons to ensure the availability and suitability of the material. Formation of a CPD program actuating team consisting of MGMP members with clear roles and responsibilities and determining a program coordinator who will lead the actuating team.

This action plan before implementing the CPD program will help MGMP to start the program with thorough and coordinated preparation. Thus, it is hoped that the program can run effectively and have a positive impact on teacher professional development.

Next is socialization. Socialization to all MGMP members before implementing the CPD is a key step to ensure participation and understanding of MGMP members regarding the program. Socialization is carried out through communication and invitations by communicating the CPD program plan to all MGMP members, sending official invitations, and including the agenda and objectives of the CPD program. With effective outreach, MGMP members can better understand and participate optimally in the CPD Program, creating an environment of positive cooperation and professional development.

Next, coordination. Coordination of the CPD program by MGMP is carried out with resource persons and facilitators in accordance with the CPD program theme and ensures that resource persons have relevant qualifications and experience. Apart from that, MGMP also coordinates with external parties such as the madrasah, the departmental development supervisor, and the madrasah education section of the Sukabumi Regency Ministry of Religion by optimizing the resources and support that can be provided by external parties.

Actuating of CPD through the in the job learning (IN 1) pattern and continued with on the job learning (ON, in each class/madrasah) and in the job learning 2 (IN 2) which is topic-based in the learning module. The activities are carried out using face-to-face and online methods. The CPD program, which is carried out internally, aims to ensure that every teacher, both civil servant and honorary, can take part in this activity.

The results of the research show that the actuating of the CPD program at MGMP 0002 and 0032 included mobilizing all MGMP members to be willing and try hard to achieve the goals sincerely and in line with the plans and organizing efforts of the MGMP Chair. This involves using influence to motivate group members and coordinating with parties to achieve the goals of the CPD program, and must be able to invite all members to actively participate in achieving these goals.

In implementing the CPD program, teachers actively build their own knowledge through experience, reflection, and interaction with the environment and other people during the CPD program. This is closely related to the philosophy of constructivism in education.

D. Controlling of the CPD Program

According to G. R. Terry (2005), controlling is the process of determining what must be achieved, namely standards, what is being done, namely actuating, assessing actuating, and if necessary making improvements, so that actuating is in accordance with the plan, that is, in line with standards (size). Monitoring/appraisal is the measurement and correction of performance to ensure that company goals and plans designed to achieve them are achieved. This is done to minimize deviations from standards and ensure that the set organizational goals are achieved in the desired manner.

Evaluation of the planning carried out by MGMP 0002 and 0032 shows that all planning stages have been carried out and adapted to the Standard Operating Procedures (POS) provided by the government, namely Decree of the Director General of Islamic Education No. 1324 of 2023

concerning Technical Instructions for Assistance to the Working Group of Teachers and Madrasah Education Personnel for the 2023 Fiscal Year.

Evaluation of the organization of the CPD program has been designed based on the Standard Operating Procedures (POS) provided by the government, namely Decree of the Director General of Islamic Education No. 1324 of 2023 concerning Technical Instructions for Assistance to the Working Group of Teachers and Madrasah Education Personnel for the 2023 Fiscal Year. Apart from that, all administrators have performed well in carrying out their duties according to the division of tasks at the program organizing stage.

Evaluation of the actuating of the CPD program can be seen from the benefits that participants get from this program. They feel that this program is very useful, namely gaining new knowledge and insight into various ways of managing the classroom with a variety of icebreakers, teaching methods and techniques that are interesting and fun for students, using information and communication technology (ICT) in learning, and making more friends. solidly with fellow Indonesian language teachers, all of which were used as learning experiences to be applied to students in their respective madrasas.

The pretest and posttest instruments assessed by Fasda to evaluate teachers' pedagogical competence indicated an increase in posttest scores compared to pretest scores. This is in accordance with the objectives to be achieved by the CPD program through the MGMP. As proof of participation in this CPD program, participants receive a certificate from the Director of Teachers and Education Personnel, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. This certificate is worth 1 Credit Point because the total training hours are 36 JP. From the evaluation of the actuating of the CPD program, it can be seen that the benefits of this program for the CPD participants are also supported by the posttest results which are better than the pretest results. Therefore, it can be concluded that teleological values color this program by referring to the evaluation of the positive impact produced by the program on participants and also the surrounding environment.

The research results show that the controlling of the CPD program in MGMP 0002 and 0032 includes a process of determining standards that must be achieved, actuating, evaluation of actuating, and making improvements so that actuating is in accordance with plans and standards. In the actuating evaluation there is performance measurement and correction to ensure the achievement of program objectives in accordance with the plans that have been made. The goal is to minimize deviations from standards and ensure that organizational goals are achieved as desired.

E. Problems faced by the CPD Program

In implementing a program there will definitely be problems or inhibiting factors, this also occurs in the actuating of the CPD program at MGMP 0002 and 0032 Indonesian MTs level in Sukabumi Regency. The first inhibiting factor in terms of attendance is that at every activity there are participants who do not attend, even though the number is small. This is because the CPD schedule clashes with the teaching schedule at the madrasah so that the head of the madrasah cannot continue to allow it. Deficiencies in the management and coordination of the

MGMP with madrasa heads can hinder the smooth actuating of activities and disrupt their effectiveness. The participants' lack of ICT mastery skills is proven by the non-use of laptops and the internet as learning media and resources to support teaching and learning activities during ON activities at their respective madrasas. In fact, during IN activities, this is used and practiced directly in class together with all participants.

Second, facilities and infrastructure. From the results of interviews, observations and documentation studies regarding facilities and infrastructure, the facilities and infrastructure in the building where the CPD was implemented were incomplete because some of the equipment was damaged. Third, costs. The costs for implementing the CPD program at MGMP 0002 and 00032 are in the form of assistance with a nominal value of IDR 30,000,000.0. For MGMP 0002, which has 27 members, it could still be said to be inadequate for 13 activities so that transportation costs for participants and facilitators are minimal even though the distance between participants and the CPD location is quite far. Participants came from all areas of Sukabumi Regency, which are quite far from each other. Meanwhile, for MGMP 0032, which has 15 members, there are no problems with financing.

F. Solutions to CPD Program Problems

Based on the problems above, the solution to the HR problem is seen in terms of attendance, where in every activity there are participants who do not attend, even though the number is small, due to clashes between the CPD schedule and the teaching schedule at the madrasah so that the head of the madrasah cannot continue to allow this approach. personal. The MGMP Chair accompanied by the Public Relations and Cooperation Division built communication with the kamads of the participants who were not 100% present. Regarding the problem of the participants' still minimal ability to master ICT as evidenced by the non-use of laptops and the internet as media and learning resources to support teaching and learning activities during ON activities in each madrasah, even though during IN activities, these are used and practiced directly in the classroom. together with all participants, the solution is to make additional meetings outside the schedule via zoom. This is to introduce the use of zoom for teachers who are still technologically illiterate with the aim of stimulating their curiosity to continue using ICT in teaching and learning activities.

Regarding the problem of facilities and infrastructure, the solution to the problem of incomplete facilities and infrastructure, infrastructure in the form of places where the CPD program takes place, chooses State MTs whose facilities tend to be better and more complete when compared to meeting buildings which are close for a small number of participants and far for the majority. participant. Facilities at State MTs are available to be used to implement the CPD program. Although some are still in good condition and some are no longer in good condition. At least, there is no need to rent facilities such as LCD projectors, sound systems, printers, etc. Meanwhile, the solution to the cost problem for implementing the CPD program at MGMP was inadequate for 13 activities for 27 people, namely by making a nominal reduction in each budget item. This is done so that activities continue well and the rights of participants and facilitators/resources are still fulfilled. This is of course discussed first with all CPD participants.

CONCLUSION

In general, it can be concluded that the management of the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs Level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the management function of G.R. Terry and the philosophy of constructivism, and also supported by Achmad Sanusi's six value systems because they have paid attention to rational logical, legal ethical and teleological values, although this has not been supported by analysis of available data so that the CPD program has not achieved the stated objectives.

In particular, it can be concluded that the planning of the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs Level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the planning concept of G.R. Terry and is also supported by a value system because it has paid attention to rational logical values.

The organization of the CPD program to improve the pedagogical competence of Indonesian language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the organizing concept of G.R. Terry and is also supported by a value system because it has paid attention to ethical-legal values. The actuating of the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the actuating concept of G.R.

Terry and is also in accordance with the philosophy of constructivism. The controlling of the CPD program in improving the pedagogical competence of Indonesian Language teachers at MGMP Indonesian Language 0002 and 0032 MTs level in Sukabumi Regency is in accordance with the controlling concept of G.R. Terry and is also supported by a value system because it has paid attention to teleological values.

The problems faced in the CPD program are the lack of teacher presence in the CPD program, the lack of mastery of ICT by teachers, the lack of complete facilities in places where the CPD program is implemented, and the lack of operational costs for MGMPs whose members are more than 25 people. The solution to the problem in the CPD program is to build effective communication with madrasa heads, lack of teacher presence in the CPD program, hold additional meetings outside the schedule through zoom meetings, choose State MTs with more complete facilities, and reduce operational costs for MGMPs with more than 25 members. person.

From the conclusion above, the idea of innovation in George R. Terry's version of CPD program management is the application of strategic management consisting of environmental analysis (ALI and ALE), strategic formulation, strategic actuating, and strategic evaluation so that the product of this research is "Hypothetical Management Model CPD Program in Improving Teacher Pedagogical Competence Based on Strategic Management" using Achmad Sanusi's six value systems in its development.

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